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Assessment of the Menace of Perennial Flood Disasters in Ilorin Metropolis, Nigeria: Towards Effective Management and Control

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ABSTRACT

Perennial flood disasters have been the haul mark of the natural disasters ravaging Ilorin metropolis in Nigeria along with concomitant human-related causes. This have resulted into significant loss of life and property. The aim of this study is to do a comprehensive assessment of the menace of flooding in the area with a view to providing necessary insights towards efficient and effective management and control. The study explores both qualitative and quantitative methods. The results show that the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.81 and the coefficient of multiple determinant (r^2) is 0.58. This means that about 58% of the variation in independent variables may be attributed to a substantial increase in the dependent variables, which are factors causing perennial floods. In addition, the F - statistics which is 12.45, was statistically significant at p -value = 0.00. These factors are rainfall, blocked waterways, and poor drainage systems, climate change, infrastructural inadequacy and dearth of funds. The study concluded by underscoring the need for effective management and control of floods in Ilorin metropolis. Against this backdrop, it was recommended that there should be effective management policies and regulations, creation of special funding window to enhance efficient and effective implementation of flood Programmes, stakeholder's engagement and collaboration to engender enhanced public awareness including the provision of improved infrastructure and adequate drainage systems. This is expected to be a step to mitigating the menace of perennial flood disasters in the study area.

Keywords: *Flood disasters, flood management, ilorin metropolis, mitigation, policies*

INTRODUCTION

Perennial flood disasters are an age long phenomenon confronting the people in Ilorin metropolis. Although floods are a natural disaster, they are most often aggravated by human-induced activities in the environment. This situation on regular basis has resulted into catastrophic consequences in terms of loss of life and property. The flood menace in the urban enclave of Ilorin presents a gory view of situations of serious and dangerous dimensions.

Flooding is a direct consequence of climate change responsible to other serious water – related severe weather spectacles. Urban flooding, whether or whether the impacted neighborhoods are situated in flood plains or close to any body of water, is defined by its recurring and systematic effects on communities, according to CNT (2013). For instance, dam failure and deliberate release of water to relief the dams of excess water constitute another means of flood disasters. At the local front, on 4th of October, 2025, the Nigeria television authority (NTA) reported that kanji, Jebba, shiroro and zungeru dams are to discharge their excess water. The annual discharges of excess water from Lago dam in Cameroon aggravates flood situation in Nigeria.

Simply put, flooding is a condition of excess water flow of higher velocity than the average volume of a river, especially during heavy downpour, dam failure and melting glazier. Factors such as elevation slope, and topographic wetness index, convergence index, and drainage density, altitude above channel, land use and rainfall are cogent factors for flood build up. These factors are considered as the most influential variables for running off accumulation and stagnation during excess rainfall and surface run-off.

Challenges to flood control include inadequate funding, poor drainage systems, and infrastructural decay among other causes environmental hazards and as such is a serious menace in Ilorin metropolis. The issue of pollution, spread of diseases, congestion and sometimes, making roads impassable for motorists, if not submerged in the city, are some of the outcomes of floods. This calls for intervention in the form of effective policies, management and sanitation facilities is essential to match up with ever increasing population growth (Banerjee and Morella, 2011)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate Change and Floods

Flood unlike other extreme weather events, are the most devastating of all geo-hazards, being the most common and with a very wide spatial spread. Globally, there is hardly any week without incidence of flood disaster around the world with varying degree of damage. Ologunorisa and Tersoo (2006) in their study established relationship between extreme rainfall flood frequencies in Makurdi in Benue state. In his study, Odjugo (2010) made the case that climate change has altered the typical length and timing of the wet and dry seasons, changed the seasonal variability of the weather and climate, and increased the seasonal fluctuation of water bodies.[1,2]

Accounts of Floods Incident in Nigeria and Some Parts of Africa

Olanrewaju, Buku and Akpan (2017) in their study discovered that flood is a serious disaster in Warri Metropolis, and it is climate dependent, most prevalent in the months of June, July and August, same month's rainfall amount and intensity are at their peak in the metropolis. The influx of people to Ilorin metropolis in search of white-collar job or other purposes has provided market for businesses to thrive. This causes increase in land consumption

and land use changes as observed by Olanrewaju (2016). Hence, high urban population growth rate results in drainage systems issues because this growth leads to pressure on the existing facilities which cannot match up with the exodus of people. This is in tandem with the position held by (Belete, 2011). This, is why, according to Blaike (2004) the impact is more felt by the urban poor who must receive external aid to be able to recover.[3,4]

Flood occurrences on the local front in Ilorin metropolis have been a recurring one with significant impacts on the residents and seriously having a toll on the infrastructure. In the last five years, in 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025, significant flood events occurred. In October 6, 2020 floods affected several states in Nigeria including Kwara and does not spare Ilorin metropolis. In the incident, 91,254 people and 15,209 households were affected. In 2023, incidents of floods took its perennial form as it was reported in various parts of Nigeria and Africa. Precisely, flash floods occurred in Buea, Cameroon, while flooding in Malawi displaced thousands of people and caused widespread damage. In June of same year, Rwanda witnessed heavy downpour that caused flooding and landslide which resulted into many deaths.

Several flood incidents are being reported on annual basis in many states in Nigeria till date including Kwara and affects the Ilorin metropolis. Some of these multitudes of heavy rainfall have resulted in deaths while properties worth billions of naira were destroyed. These flood related incidents in Ilorin metropolis in particular and Nigeria as a whole provide insight into the challenges of floods in the study area.[5]

AN OVERVIEW OF FLOODS GLOBALLY

Floods are one of the most terrific and catastrophic disasters. Smith and Ward (1998) cited in Olanrewaju, Buku and Akpan (2018) stated that global floods regularly claim over 20,000 lives per day and adversely affected about 75 million people. Climatological and non-climatological factors is attributed to the occurrence of floods. Ayoade (2003) also buttressed the above assertion and added that intense and heavy rainfall accounts for the majority of floods that occur in the tropical regions. The impacts of climate change cannot be ignored, it has and will continue to play major role in flood occurrence, its frequency and intensity. The mutual relationship between man and weather and climate often lead to both positive and negative consequences, one of which is the occurrence of disasters. Disaster has different classifications, and types, its occurrence, severity or at least the management is directly or indirectly influenced by climate change (Oxfam, 2019).

The incidences of heavy rainfall is a crucial element of hydrological disaster that result in flood. Physiopedia (2019) and Wikipedia (2019) reported that between 1995-2015 its Emergency Event Database (EMDAT) recorded 6,457 weather-related disasters which claimed a total of 606,000 lives and affected more than 4 billion people. Average of 205 million people are affected annually by weather and climate related disasters. It equally revealed that poor countries were disproportionately affected due to their intrinsic vulnerabilities to hazards and comparatively low capacities for disaster management. From the economic perspectives, Banis (2019) examined the report given by the United Kingdom's charity organization, "Christian aid", published in 2018. It focused on the financial implication of climate-change

driven weather events over the past year in various parts of the world. The 4th, 6th and 8th of the 10 most expensive climate change-related disasters in 2018 by area are respectively

- (a) Japan – floods: \$7billion (June – July floods)
- (b) China – floods : \$3.9 billion (July floods)
- (c) India (Kerela) – floods : \$3.7 billion

Flood remains a global phenomenon in which the local imprints also hits remarkably. Outside the influence of the rains and urbanization due to the need to satisfy the increasing population explosion, pressure have impacted the drainage systems. This is known to have significant effects on the people's means of livelihood and sometimes claims life and destroy properties amounting to serious economic losses. It becomes imperative to design implementable solutions in order to ameliorate the condition of the people in Ilorin metropolis.[6]

Research Questions

The research questions below are stated in order to ascertain the objectives

- Are there significant relationships between environmental factors and perennial floods in Ilorin metropolis?
- Do floods have significant impacts on the study area's infrastructure and economy?
- Are there specific locations in the study area that are more prone to flooding?
- Is there a significant relationship between flood occurrences and people's livelihoods in the study area?
- Do existing mitigation, control and management strategies pose significant challenges to efficient and effective flood management in the study area?

OBJECTIVE (S) OF THE STUDY

This research assessed the menace of the perennial flood disasters in Ilorin metropolis with a view to instituting a mitigating solution for effective management and control.

The Specific Objectives to be able to Achieve the Aim are to:

- determine the causes of perennial floods in Ilorin metropolis;
- examine the effects of floods in the study area;
- investigate the impacts of flooding on the people of Ilorin metropolis and their property; and
- identify flash points or hotspots of floods in the study area and evaluate the challenges to efficient and effective flood mitigation

Research

Hypotheses

The hypotheses below were formulated to guide as an aid in obtaining results of the experimental study.

- Ho: There is no significant relationship between urbanization, poor drainage systems and heavy rainfall and the occurrence of perennial floods in Ilorin metropolis
- Ho: Floods have no significant impact on the socio-economic well-being of residents in Ilorin metropolis
- Ho: There is no significant difference in the impact of flooding on people and property in different location within Ilorin metropolis
- Ho: There is no significant relationship between the challenges posed by flood mitigation and effectiveness of flood management efforts in Ilorin metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Ilorin is located between latitude $8^{\circ}26'1''$ and $8^{\circ}30'1''$ North of the equator and between longitude $4^{\circ}31'1''$ and $4^{\circ}36'1''$ East of

the Greenwich meridian. Its geology is underlined by basement complex rocks of the precombrian ages (Ajibade and Oyelola, 2004). Ilorin is traversed by River Asa which follows North-South direction and tributaries like Oyun and Aluko rivers dividing the plain location into Western and Eastern. It also has River Niger as its natural boundaries along the Northern and Eastern Margin. The Eastern part is generally steeper with height ranging from 900-1200 feet in some parts and peaking at an isolated landform, sobi hill which is about 1,300 feet above sea level (Oyebanji, 1993).[7]

Ocean begins from march to October and results into eight Months rainy season of double maxima rainfall pattern reaching its peak in June and September. October remains the pivotal transition month in Nigeria's annual climate cycle (ANCCE, Unijos, 2025). The tropical continental air mass from Sahara Desert begins from November to February resulting into four months' dry season (Olaniran 2002). The annual rainfall of Ilorin averaged 1500mm, the minimum temperature ranges from 21⁰C to 25⁰C with average maximum at 38⁰C. There is 7.1 hours of sunshine each day and a relative humidity of 77.5% (Olawajaju, 2009).

Ilorin is typical of wet and dry climate. The tropical air mass from the Atlantic

Fig. 1: Map of Ilorin Metropolis

Source: ResearchGate

RESEARCH DESIGN

The descriptive and inferential research design based on survey method was employed in this study. A set of structured and semi-structured questionnaires to elicit information from the selected sampled

population in Ilorin metropolis was used after been projected from 2006 to 2024 at 2.6% annual growth rate. Tarro Yamane (1973) Statistical formula was adopted to calculate and obtain the sample of 400 respondents in the study area which was

stratified into 16 flash points proportionally to administer 25 (sample size) questionnaires in each of the GIS identified flash points locations to eliminate bias. Geography Information System (GIS) analysis was used to analyze flood risk mapping and management.

Primary data was obtained from interview and through the instrument of questionnaire administration by personal delivery of the researcher in conjunction with research assistants. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed out of which 320 were meticulously retrieved. The primary data were subjected to coding and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, after which analytic techniques such as Analysis of variance (ANOVA), linear and multiple regression

N_t = projected population in 2024
 p = initial population (2006) = 777,657
 e = base of natural logarithms = 2.71828
 t = time period = 2024 – 2006 = 18 years
 $N_t = 777,657 \times e^{(0.026 \times 18)}$
 $= 777,657 \times e^{(0.468)}$
 $= 777,657 \times 1.596$
 $N_t = 1,242,111$

Tarro Yamane formula was adopted to calculate the sample size because it is suitable for large population and ensures results are reliable and generalizable as expressed by Mertler Vennatta (2005) and used by Asadu *et al*, (2018) as follows $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ where,

n = sample size
 N = population size = 1,242,111
 e = margin of error = 0.05 (5%)
 $n = \frac{1,242,111}{1 + 1,242,111(0.05)^2} = \frac{1,242,111}{1 + 1,242,111(0.0025)} = \frac{1,242,111}{1 + 3105.2775} = 399.85 = 400$ Approximately

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed with the aid of both descriptive and inferential methods of statistics. Descriptive statistics was activated by the use of tools like tabulation, measure of central tendencies, percentile and charts. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze some of the stated objective as depicted below:

analysis and chi-square were used to analyze the data. SPSS 13.0 software package was deployed for the triangulation of both the qualitative and quantitative data in order to obtain a better result.[8]

Sampling Frame, Sample Size and Procedure

The population of the research work covered the population of the entire 3 local governments that constitute Ilorin metropolis namely, Ilorin West, Ilorin South and Ilorin East with a total population of 777,650 (NPC, 2006).

In determining the sample size for the study, the population was projected from 2006 to 2024 at 2.6% annual growth rate using the formula $N_t = p * e^{(rt)}$ where,

Objective i: to determine the causes of perennial floods, multiple regression model was used to identify significant predictors of flooding:

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \dots + \beta_{10} X_{10} + e$$

The dependent variable is flood occurrence while independent variables is rainfall

Objective ii: to examine the effects of floods, descriptive statistics was used such as mean, frequency count and ANOVA to examine the impacts of floods on infrastructure and economy which is the dependent variable

Objective iii: Geographic Information System (GIS) analysis was used to identify the flash points of floods in the area with drainage as independent variable.

Objective iv: linear regression analysis was used to examine the relationship between flood occurrences and people's livelihoods being the dependent variable while flood occurrences is the independent variable.

Objective: descriptive statistics and inferential Chi-Square test was used to examine the challenges posed by existing strategies. Flood mitigation and management strategies is the independent variable.

RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENTS

The use of mix-methods in data collection principles and methodologies ensures data reliability including the reconnaissance is a test case for reliability. The instruments for data collection were well-designed, consistently administered and collected following standard procedures for

consistency and precision which provides basis for reliability of the instruments. Interviews conducted to establish facts from questionnaires provides a basis for validity and confirmation test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 is the presentation of the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. 69.1% of them were male within the study area thereby dominating the female who are 30.9% indicating gender disparity in terms of population distribution. The largest age group falls within age bracket 41-50 years (42.2%) and closely followed by those above 50 years (25.7%). This trend implies that most of the respondents are of age relatively not within young productive year. They were followed by 31-40 years (21.85%) and 18-30 years (10.6%) respectively.

The marital status indicated that a big Chunk of 57.2% of the respondents are married. With regards to educational qualifications, majority of them are SSCE holders who shared 30%. This implies that a significant proportion of respondents are slightly above basic education level. 42.1% of the respondents earned monthly income of #70,000 within the Nigeria's minimum wage threshold limit. This income level is poor considering the inflation rate especially the married who will be responsible for family upkeep.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents	Frequency (n) = 320	Percentage%
Sex		
Male	221	69.1
Female	99	30.9
Age		
18-30	34	10.6
31-40	69	21.5
41-50	135	42.2
Above 50	82	25.7
Marital Status		
Single	32	10

Married	183	57.2
Divorced	28	8.7
Widow/ Widower	77	24.1
Educational Qualification		
First school leaving certification	67	21
SSCE	96	30
NCE	82	25.6
OND	36	11.3
HND	21	6.5
B.S.C & Above	18	5.6
Monthly Income		
Less than 70,000	135	42.1
70,001 - 80,000	78	24.4
80,001 - 90,000	54	16.9
90,001 – 100,000	36	11.3
Above 100,000	17	5.3
Source: Author’s Field Computation (2025)		

The causes of the perennial floods in Ilorin Metropolis are determined by a combination of factors including rainfall, blocked waterways, poor drainage, and climate change among others. The results of the multiple regression analysis

depicting flood occurrence = $\beta_0 + \beta_1$ (Rainfall) + β_2 (Blocked waterways) + β_3 (Poor drainage) + ϵ are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Determination of the Cause of Perennial Floods.

Predictors	Unstandardized coefficient β	Standard error	T	Sig.
Rainfall	0.45	0.12	3.75	0.001
Blocked Waterways	0.23	0.10	2.30	0.022
Poor Drainage	0.18	0.09	2.00	0.046
$R^2 = 0.65$, F-Statistic = 12.45, P-Value = 0.000				
Source: Author’s Field Computation, (2025)				

Table 2 shows that rainfall, blocked waterways and poor drainage are the major causes of the perennial flood occurrences with their P-Values lesser than 0.05 which is statistically significant as predictors of floods in the study area. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) value of 0.58 signifies that 58% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables included in the model. This leaves 42% of the variance

attributable to other factors not captured in this study.

The overall significance of the regression model is confirmed. An F- statistic of 12.45, which is statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) allows one to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the predictor variables reliably predicts the causes related to perennial flooding and that the model fits for the data.

Table 3: Model Summary.

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
1	0.81	0.65	0.58
Predictors: Rainfall, Blocked Waterways, Poor Drainage			
Source: Author's Field Computation, (2025)			

As presented in Table 3, the multiple correlation coefficient R of 0.81 reveals a strong positive relationship between the set of independent variables (Rainfall, blocked

waterways, poor drainage) and the dependent variable (Flood occurrence). Thus, the regression analysis reveals a robust model of prediction.

Table 4: Examination of the effects of floods.

Predictors	Mean	Standard deviation
Loss of Livelihood	4.20	1.20
Damage to property	3.80	1.10
Displacement	4.50	1.00
ANOVA: F-Statistic= 10.25, P-Value= 0.000		
SOURCE: Author's Field Computation, (2025)		

The results in table 4 indicates that flood have significance impact on infrastructure and economy considering the 10.25 F-ratio to standard and P-Value 0.000 which are both statistically significant to reject

the null hypothesis. The import of this is that the Socio-economic well-being of the people is significantly hampered in the advent of floods in the metropolis.

Table 5: Investigating the Impacts of floods on lives and property

Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Standard	T	P-value
Flood Occurrence	0.50	0.10	5.00	0.000
R ² = 0.40, F-Statistic= 25.00, P=Value 0.000				
SOURCE: Author's Field Computation, (2025)				

In Table 5, the results of the linear regression has people's livelihood as the dependent variable= $\beta_0 + \beta_1$ (Floods occurrence) + ϵ . The regression coefficient (R²) value of 0.40 reveals that floods occurrence has a significant impact on people's livelihood. The large F-Statistic of 25.00 value shows that the model is significant thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. The P-Value 0.000 < 0.05

indicates that floods occurrence is statistically significant.

To identify the flash points of floods in the study area, Geographic Information System (GIS) was used to analyze flood risk and mapping. The results indicated that low-lying areas, drainage channels and streams are common flash points indicating the extent of flood severity (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Map showing flood flash points within Ilorin metropolis.

Source: Author’s reconnaissance survey, 2025

Table 6: Evaluating the challenge to flood mitigation effectiveness

Predictors	X ²	df	P-Value
Infrastructure inadequacy	12.10	3	0.007
Poor drainage	8.50	2	0.014
SOURCE: Author’s Field Computation, (2025)			

In table 6, the Chi-Square test results of 12.10 show that there is a significant relationship between infrastructure inadequacy and flood mitigation effectiveness as well as the P-Value of 0.007 at (P< 0.05) and the degree of freedom. Poor drainage presents similar outcome. Hence, both infrastructure inadequacy and poor drainage posed significant challenges to flood mitigation efforts in Ilorin Metropolis.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study underscores the need for effective flood management and control in Ilorin metropolis. It is expected that the insights into the critical causes and effects of floods and their impacts will provide better understanding towards developing and implementing remedial interventions. This is hoped to be a step to mitigating the menace of perennial flood disasters in the study area. The study was able to provide policy basis for improved infrastructure and drainage systems and a blue print for effective flood management which

enhances public awareness and stakeholders' engagement and participation in flood management endeavors in Ilorin metropolis.

The study's identification of the hot spots location for flood should be a wakeup call to both the government and public on disaster preparedness and possible mitigation strategies. The flood-prone areas identified should inform the step towards flood hazards zone susceptibility mapping and an opportunity for understanding flood risk management.

The following recommendations were made including:

- Need for effective flood management policies and regulations Beyond early warning of the imminent happening and danger of floods, effort should be made towards prevention strategies, where possible on potential victims of flood occurrence. Country planning authority must be seen to be effective in implementing relevant laws guiding location and construction of houses and other landed properties. When people refrain from building within the precinct of flood sphere of influence, dangers can be averted, if not completely eliminated
- Creation of special funding window to enhance efficient and effective implementation of flood management policies and programmes. Government should "walk the talk" on promises to flood victims during emergency and be forthcoming in discharging its social responsibility when it comes to compensation. Flood situation can be converted into strength rather than weakness by seeing it as opportunity to refocus on converting the waste of flood to wealth. A lot of agricultural potential opportunities presents from flood occurrences because the flood nourishes the nutrient of the soil which

can be of immense value for agricultural productivity.

- Provision of improved infrastructure and adequate drainage systems. Government can use the floods to initiate and create water bank by constructing platforms or edifices that can store the flood water for various uses e.g. irrigation purposes, water treatment solution for re-use among other uses.
- Stakeholders engagement and collaboration to engender enhanced public awareness

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